

Endodontic Management And Prosthetic Rehabilitation of Maxillary Central Incisor With Internal Root Resorption: A Case Report

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Abstract

Internal root resorption is a rare clinical condition which occurs due to complex interaction of resorbing and inflammatory cells in permanent dentition. It is characterized by resorption on the inner surface of dentine adjacent to the granulation tissue produced in the pulp. Internal resorptions are evident in only 1- 2% of clinical cases and are usually asymptomatic. The most consistent explanation for the occurrence of internal resorption associated pulpal granulation tissue is inflammation or trauma of the pulp tissue. The progression of internal root resorption depends on the presence of vital tissue in the root canal. If it is left undetected or remains untreated, then it may continue to advance and perforate the inner root surface. This case report emphasizes on the endodontic management and aesthetic restoration of maxillary left central incisor with internal root resorption.

Keywords: Internal root resorption, Dental pulp, Bioceramic sealer, Maxillary left central incisor

Introduction

Dental resorption is defined as the loss of dental hard tissues as a result of clastic activities.¹ Root resorption in primary dentition is a physiologic process except if it occurs prematurely. Resorption in permanent dentition is a pathologic process which may result in premature loss of the affected teeth. Depending on location in relation to the root surface, resorption may be classified as 'external and internal'.

External root resorption affects the outer surface of the root and is usually a consequence to dental luxation and avulsion. Internal root resorption (IRR) is defined as the progressive destruction of intraradicular dentine and dentinal tubules along the root canal walls from clastic activity.² Based on limited studies and clinical experience of authors, the prevalence of patients affected by IRR is very low and suggested to be between 0.01% to 2%.³ The clinical characteristics of IRR are dependent on the development and location of resorption. Most teeth with IRR are asymptomatic. However, in some cases when the resorption is actively progressing, the tooth is partially vital and may present symptoms typical of pulpitis.

Radiographically, it is evident as a radiolucent area which is characterized by an oval shaped enlargement of the root canal.⁴ IRR can occur in the cervical third,

middle third and apical third region of the root.

If the resorption occurs in the cervical third region, then in advanced cases, crown appears pink or reddish in color due to the presence of very thin enamel layer. The pink or reddish hue is caused by highly vascularized connective tissue adjacent to resorbing cells.⁵ Teeth with untreated internal resorptions in the coronal area often turn gray/dark gray after pulp necrosis.³

Case Report

A 55 year old female patient reported to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics at Chandra Dental College and Hospital with the chief complaint of decayed tooth. On clinical and radiographic examination, tooth #21 had deep caries reaching the pulp chamber and internal resorption in the middle third of the root along with periapical radiolucency around the root apex (Fig.1). The palpation and percussion tests produced mild responses. The history revealed that the patient had trauma to the tooth about a year ago. Also, patient has mentioned that she is

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under anti-asthmatic drug medication since 8 years which restricted the use of rubber dam during treatment.

When patient's history, clinical and radiographic examinations were combined, the diagnosis of this case was made as chronic periapical pathosis with internal root resorption. So, we planned root canal treatment followed by prosthesis in #21. Patient was thoroughly informed about the treatment plan and a written consent was obtained from her.

Local anesthesia was administered using 2% Lignocaine with 1:80,000 adrenaline (Lignox, Indoco Remedies Ltd, India). Caries in the coronal portion was completely removed and the access cavity was prepared in tooth #21. ISO #10K size file was inserted upto full length of the canal and an intra oral periapical radiograph was taken to determine the working length (Fig. 2). The root canal was instrumented with rotary NiTi files using crown down technique. Root canal was finally prepared till master apical file size #30 and 0.06 taper (Fig. 3). During biomechanical preparation, sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) and ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA) were used as irrigating solutions. After that the root canal was dried with sterile paper points and calcium hydroxide dressing was applied. The access cavity was restored with temporary restorative material (Cavit). One week later in the second visit, the tooth was asymptomatic. Intracanal calcium hydroxide dressing was removed using hand instrumentation with copious irrigation of root canal using NaOCl and EDTA irrigating solutions. Final irrigation of the root canal was done using distilled water. The root canal was dried with sterile paperpoints and obturated with warm vertical condensation technique using thermoplasticized guttapercha (Denjoy Cordless GuttaPercha Obturation System) and bioceramic sealer (SafeEndo BioActive RCS) (Fig. 4). The access cavity was restored with glass ionomer cement. After 1 month clinical and radiographic follow up examination, the tooth was in healthy state. Tooth preparation for all ceramic crown was done in #21 followed by prosthesis cementation. Patient was very satisfied with the final treatment outcome (Fig. 5, 6 and 7). After 6 months follow up, clinical examination showed no pain and inflammation irt #21 and radiographic evaluation revealed that the periapical radiolucency was significantly reduced and did not represent any sign of further internal resorption (Fig. 8).

Fig. 1 Preoperative Radiograph irt #21

Fig. 2 Working Length Determination Radiograph

Fig. 3 Mastercone Radiograph

Fig. 4 Post Obturation Radiograph

Fig. 5 Tooth Preparation irt #21 for Prosthesis

Fig. 6 Prosthesis Cementation (Facial Aspect)

Fig. 7 Prosthesis Cementation (Palatal Aspect)

Fig. 8 Follow up Radiograph after 6 Months

Discussion

Internal root resorption is a multidisciplinary matter of concern to the clinicians, especially the Endodontists. It is a complex interaction of resorbing and inflammatory cells in permanent teeth.⁶ The vascular changes in the pulp subsequent to traumatic dental injury, mechanical forces from orthodontic treatment, high heat buildup during tooth preparation without adequate water-cooling initiate hyperemia.⁷ Active hyperemia increases local oxygen tension, lowers pH and alters metabolism of pulp leading to attract numerous macrophages which eventually differentiate into osteoclasts. Finally, the connective tissue undergoes metaplasia and changes into granulation tissue.⁸

Histologically, internal resorption can present with different manifestations based on pattern and extent of resorption as described below in figure 9.⁹

Fig. 9 Subtypes of Internal Root Resorption

The progression of internal root resorption depends upon the presence of vital tissue in the root canal. If the lesion is not detected or remains untreated, it grows and perforates the root surface from inside.¹⁰ However, in cases without perforation root canal treatment is sufficient but in cases where perforation is present, root canal treatment should be followed by repair of perforation site. In our case, internal resorption may have been triggered by trauma and the resorption area was moderate and surrounded by dentinal wall. So, we preferred root canal treatment for present case.

One of the important goals of achieving successful treatment in internal resorption cases is to completely fill the root cavity.¹¹ The filling material must be fluid for absolute sealing of the resorbed area. In present case, the root canal walls were coated with bioceramic sealer and the canal was filled with thermoplasticized guttapercha using warm vertical compaction technique followed by post endodontic restoration of glass ionomer cement. For longevity of the endodontic treatment, tooth #21 was rehabilitated with an all-ceramic prosthesis. After 6 months follow up examination, the tooth #21 was completely asymptomatic.

Conclusion

Correct diagnosis, proper treatment planning of the root resorption is essential for a successful treatment outcome. Internal resorption cases are rare and usually asymptomatic but they may require different treatment protocols depending upon their progression. Regular recall is important to investigate the healing status and overall prognosis of the affected tooth.

References

1. Patel S, Ford TP: Is the resorption external or internal? Dent Update, 2007, Vol 34(4):218-220, 222, 224-6, 229.
2. Sangeeta Kulkarni, Sangeetha Singh: Management of root resorption- a case report; Saudi J. Med. Pharma. Sci., 2016, Vol-2, (7):170-175.
3. Markus Haaapasalo & Unni Endal: Internal inflammatory root resorption: the unknown resorption of the tooth; Endodontic Topics, 2006, Vol-14:60-79.
4. Pankaj Yadav, Yogesh Rao, Anurag Jain et al: Treatment of internal resorption with mineral trioxide aggregates: a case report; Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research, 2013, Vol-7(10): 2400-2401.
5. Patel S, Ricucci D and Tay F: Internal root resorption: a review; J. Endod, 2010, Vol-36:1107-1121.
6. Gunes Karakaya, Gorkem Can, Dilek Turkeydin et al: Treatment of maxillary central incisors with internal resorption: two case reports; Turk Endod J, 2019, Vol 4(2):39-43.
7. Patel S, Saberi N: The ins and outs of root resorption; Br Dent J, 2018, Vol 224(9): 691-699.
8. Robinowitch BZ: Internal resorption; Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol, 1972, Vol 33(2):263-282.
9. Kirsty A. Carney, Thibault N. E. Colloc, Julie K. Kilgariff: Management of rarely seen internal tunnelling root resorption associated with a maxillary permanent incisor; British Dental Journal, 2024, Vol 236(12).
10. Stamos DE, Stamos DG: A new treatment modality for internal resorption; J Endod, 1986, Vol-12(7): 315-319.
11. Parisa Sanaei-rad, Marjan Bolbolian, Faranak Nouri et al: Management of internal root resorption in the maxillary central incisor with fractured root using biodentine; Clin Case Rep, 2021, Vol 9.